

D8.13

Atmospheric subdomain FAIRness assessment report

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Deliverable abstract

This report presents the implementation of the FAIR principles across the atmospheric subdomain over the ENVRI-FAIR project period.

The report starts with the introduction and background for the baseline for the FAIR implementation of the atmospheric subdomain. Subsequently, the progress, achievements, and status of FAIRness within the atmospheric subdomain is described in 2 levels. Section 2.1 documents the progress and FAIRness in accordance with the implementation plan, whereas section 2.2 reports a summary and assessment of the FAIR implementation Profile (FIP), including FAIR convergence within the atmospheric subdomain. A section comparing the atmospheric sub-domain with all the environmental domain is also included. The final section 3 gives a summary of the main achievements for the atmospheric subdomain and highlights what can be done now compared to the start of the work in 2019.

DELIVERY SLIP

	Name	Partner Organization	Date
Main Author	Cathrine Lund Myhre Markus Fiebig Richard O. Rud Lucia Mona Claudio Dema Patrice Henry Bénédicte Picquet-Varrault	ACTRIS/NILU, Norway ACTRIS/NILU, Norway ACTRIS/NILU, Norway ACTRIS/NILU, Norway ACTRIS/CNR-IMAA, Italy ACTRIS/CNES/AERIS, France ACTRIS/IPSL/LISA, France	19 May 2023
Contributing Authors	Cathy Boonne Guillaume Brissebrat Ewan O'Connor Simo Tukiainen Damian Boulanger Leo Rivier Alex Vermeulen Lara Ferrighi	ACTRIS/CNRS/AERIS, France ACTRIS/CNRS/AERIS ACTRIS/FMI, Finland ACTRIS/FMI, Finland IAGOS/CNRS/AERIS, France ICOS/LSCE, France ICOS ERIC, Sweden MET Norway/SIOS, Norway	19 May 2023
Reviewer(s)	Paolo Laj	University, Grenoble, France	1 June 2023
Approver	Andreas Petzold	IAGOS/FZJ/Germany	12 June 2023

DELIVERY LOG

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V 0.1	19 May 2023		Cathrine Lund Myhre

DOCUMENT AMENDMENT PROCEDURE

Amendments, comments and suggestions should be sent to the Project Manager at manager@envri-fair.eu.

GLOSSARY

A relevant project glossary is included in Appendix A. The latest version of the master list of the glossary is available at <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4471374>.

PROJECT SUMMARY

ENVRI-FAIR is the connection of the ESFRI Cluster of Environmental Research Infrastructures (ENVRI) to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Participating research infrastructures (RI) of the environmental domain cover the subdomains Atmosphere, Marine, Solid Earth and Biodiversity / Ecosystems and thus the Earth system in its full complexity.

The overarching goal is that at the end of the proposed project, all participating RIs have built a set of FAIR data services which enhances the efficiency and productivity of researchers, supports innovation, enables data- and knowledge-based decisions and connects the ENVRI Cluster to the EOSC.

This goal is reached by: (1) well defined community policies and standards on all steps of the data life cycle, aligned with the wider European policies, as well as with international developments; (2) each participating RI will have sustainable, transparent and auditable data services, for each step of data life cycle, compliant to the FAIR principles. (3) the focus of the proposed work is put on the implementation of prototypes for testing pre-production services at each RI; the catalogue of prepared services is defined for each RI independently, depending on the maturity of the involved RIs; (4) the complete set of thematic data services and tools provided by the ENVRI cluster is exposed under the EOSC catalogue of services.

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D8.13 - Atmospheric subdomain FAIRness assessment report

1 Introduction and background

The ENVRI-FAIR project's objective is to implement "FAIRness" for data produced in the European Research Infrastructures (RIs) organized in the Environmental Research Infrastructures (ENVRI) community, in order to make them ready for connecting to the [European Open Science Cloud \(EOSC\)](#). In this context, "FAIR" is an acronym comprising the aspects of "Findable", "Accessible", "Interoperable", and "Reusable" as specified by the [FORCE11 community](#).

ENVRI-FAIR WP8 organises and conducts this implementation work for the community of ENVRI RIs in the atmospheric subdomain, comprised of the RIs [ACTRIS](#), [EISCAT](#), [IAGOS](#), [ICOS \(atmosphere\)](#), and [SIOS \(atmosphere\)](#). See Box 1 for more information about the RIs.

The main objective for the atmospheric domain within ENVRI-FAIR has been to advance the FAIRness of the atmospheric subdomain, by implementation of technological solutions on RI level to improve access to data and services. The atmospheric RIs agreed to a main strategy and goal:

"To increase use of data for all users by learning from each other and take advantage of synergies and common solutions when feasible and beneficial to serve our existing users and attract and serve new users."

This deliverable documents the FAIRness of the RIs across the atmospheric subdomain by March 2023, and highlights the common achievements, synergies, and convergence of FAIRness across the subdomain.

The atmospheric RIs within ENVRI landscape are targeting

- Climate change, both natural and anthropogenic changes
- Air pollution and air quality,
- Natural hazards impacting the atmosphere as fires, desert storms, extreme precipitation,
- Space weather with impact on surface infrastructures and on satellite communication.

The RIs compile in total at least 130 variables on atmospheric composition or properties, of which ca 75 variables are reactive trace gases, distributed over 5 RIs. The RIs are handling data in RRT (< 3 hour), NRT (< 3 days), and quality assured data. The 5 RIs are covering the atmospheric subdomain, including 2 multidomain RIs with an atmospheric component (ICOS and SIOS). The RIs are:

 ACTRIS – Aerosol Cloud and Trace gases Research Infrastructure

 EISCAT-3D European Incoherent Scatter radar system

 IAGOS – In-service Aircraft for a Global Observing System

 ICOS – atm: Integrated Carbon Observation System – atmospheric component

 SIOS-atm: Svalbard Integrated Arctic

1.1 Definition of FAIR

We refer to the [GO-FAIR¹](#) initiative to describe the FAIR principles, as these are used in ENVRI-FAIR and the work across all subdomains. The following definitions and descriptions are used:

Findable

The first step in (re)using data is to find them. This principle is defined in 4 sub-principles used:

- F1. (Meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier.
- F2. Data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below).
- F3. Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data they describe.
- F4. (Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource.

Accessible

Once the user finds the required data, she/he/they need to know how they can be accessed, possibly including authentication and authorization.

- A1. (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communications protocol. A1.1 The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable.
- A1.2 The protocol allows for an authentication and authorisation procedure, where necessary.
- A2. Metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available.

Interoperable

The data usually need to be integrated with other data. In addition, the data need to interoperate with applications or workflows for analysis, storage, and processing.

- I1. (Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.
- I2. (Meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles.
- I3. (Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data.

Reusable

The ultimate goal of FAIR is to optimize the reuse of data. To achieve this, metadata and data should be well-described so that they can be replicated and/or combined in different settings. R1. (Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes.

- R1.1. (Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license.
- R1.2. (Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance.
- R1.3. (Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards.

These sub-principles are used in the work, description and assessments of FAIRness.

1.2 FAIR profiles definition – the use of FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIP)

In an effort to accelerate convergence on FAIR implementation options, the GO FAIR¹ community has launched the development of machine-actionable FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIP). An essential criterion for FAIRness is not only the implementation of the FAIR service itself, but also the choice of technology for it, i.e. the choice of FAIR Enabling Resource (FER). Choosing the same FERs to implement in a community to implement FAIRness leads to FAIR convergence. The FIPs issued from ENVRI-FAIR joint activity are a representation of the implementation choices of different communities, and additionally quantify FAIR convergence. They can be used to follow the evolution of FAIR data services and the convergence between communities. Over the project period there have been FIPs to assess the FAIRness across the environmental domain. The FIPs are based on implementation of the FAIR Enabling Resource (FER) types defined in ENVRI-FAIR (WP5) and listed below.

¹ [FAIR Principles - GO FAIR \(go-fair.org\)](#)

Table 1: FAIR Enabling Resource (FER) types defined in ENVRI-FAIR

FAIR principle	FAIR enabling resource types
F1	Identifier type
F2	Metadata schema
F3	Metadata-Data linking mechanism
F4	Search engines
A1.1	Communication protocol
A1.2	Authentication & authorisation technique
A2	Metadata longevity
I1	Knowledge representation language
I2	Structured vocabularies
I3	Schema/Model
R1.1	Data usage license
R1.2	Provenance model

R1.3 Community specific metadata -> the FIP as a whole

Results for the development on convergence across the atmospheric subdomain using this FERs will be described in section 2.2.

1.3 Starting point for the RI's development of FAIRness

The RIs of the ENVRI atmospheric subdomain have conducted a comprehensive analysis of the FAIRness of their data management and data centres, in several steps.

The first step was an analysis of the FAIRness of the RIs associated data centres, data curation and management in 2018 in relation to the proposal and project development of ENVRI-FAIR. This resulted in a FAIRness matrix, guiding the tasks and development of the ENVRI-FAIR project.

After the project start in January 2019, a comprehensive FAIRness assessment was performed both within the atmospheric subdomain and across all subdomains by the cross-cutting work package (WP5). This resulted in a detailed implementation plan on RI level, taking cross-RI aspects into account. [D8.3 Atmospheric subdomain implementation plan](#) is providing the implementation plan of FAIRness for the atmospheric subdomain and was ready March 2020. Later there was a revised version produced, taking the implementation of the new ENVRI-hub into account. [This 2nd version was finalized September 2021](#), and is still the employed implementation plan for the atmospheric subdomain.

2 FAIRness within the atmospheric subdomain

Within the atmospheric subdomain the evolution and priorities of each RI vary both in the needs and maturity at the start, and also importantly what is considered as the most essential steps to improve towards FAIRness for the RI users. Improving convergence within the atmospheric subdomain and seek for harmonized solutions is also an important goal and has to balance the RI specific needs.

Section 2.1 documents the improvement of FAIRness of each of the specific atmospheric RIs, while section 2.2 shows the convergence within the subdomain as of March 2023.

2.1 Implementation of FAIRness within the atmospheric subdomain

This section summarizes the status of implementation of FAIRness within the atmospheric subdomain as of April 2023 in relation to the [implementation plan](#).

The gap analysis and 1st FAIRness assessment (described in section 1.3) defines the core tasks to be implemented at RI level for the atmospheric subdomain. The identified gaps considered most important from a user perspective concern the following FAIRness functions across this subdomain RIs

- **Findable:** globally unique identifier; indexed in searchable resource.
- **Accessible:** (meta)data retrievable by standardised protocol
- **Interoperable:** common vocabulary
- **Re-usable:** established license, documented provenance, (meta)data meets community standards.

Summary tables for each RI with the evolution of FAIRness over the period 2019 – 2022 based on the goals set in the implementation plan [D8.3 Atmospheric subdomain implementation plan](#) documents the tasks implemented, and the achievements over the period 2019 - 2022. The symbols used are

	Completed
	In progress
	Not started, according to plan (0)
	New tasks not in the implementation plan

More details on the results presented in the following sections 2.1.1 to 2.1.5 is available in the RI specific reports:

- **D8.4: The FAIRness of ACTRIS;**
- **D8.5: The FAIRness of EISCAT_3D;**
- **D8.6: The FAIRness of IAGOS;**
- **D8.7: The FAIRness of ICOS-atm;**
- **D8.8: The FAIRness of SIOS;**

2.1.1 ACTRIS Data Centre and the progress of FAIRness over the period 2019 – 2022

ACTRIS DC consists of various distributed data centre units. The numerous measurement methodologies applied in ACTRIS result in a considerable diversity of the data collected. In accordance with these requirements, ACTRIS DC is organized in 6 Units, with clear links and procedures for interaction between the data centre Units, National Facilities (NFs) and topical centres (TCs). There are 5 units with complementary topic expertise and 1 unit with integrating activities (DVAS) and the main entrance for users. However, the development of DVAS and DVAS FAIRness relies on the contributing DC units. Accordingly, the development in all units is included here. In this report the implementation and progress within each unit is shown.

Figure 1: Architecture of the ACTRIS Data Centre

Table 2: Summary of implementation of FAIRness within ACTRIS -DVAS

Task and Milestones under implementation	Due month Implementation plan	Status June 2020	Status November 2022	Status February 2023
1.1 Use of PIDs throughout workflow				
ACTRIS: determine PID solution	3rd QTR 20			
ACTRIS: implement primary DOIs	1st QTR 22			
ACTRIS: PIDs pre-products implemented	4th QTR 22			
ACTRIS: ORCID and org. PIDs implemented	4th QTR 22			
1.2 Standard interfaces for (meta)data access				
ACTRIS: metadata repository, 1st version	4th QTR 21			
ACTRIS: metadata M2M interface available	3rd QTR 22			
ACTRIS: THREDDS data repository and interfaces	4th QTR 21			
1.3 Data indexing in WIS and GEOSS				
ACTRIS: link to GISC in WIS implemented	4th QTR 22			
1.4 Common authentication schemes				
ACTRIS: ORCID authentication implemented	4th QTR 22			
1.5 Service endpoint to ENVRI-hub				
ACTRIS: set up PythonAPI endpoint	3rd QTR 22			
ACTRIS: provide service record	3rd QTR 21			
1.6 GUI recommendations				
ACTRIS: new portal dev. kick-off	2nd QTR 21			
ACTRIS: new portal test release	2nd QTR 22			
ACTRIS: new portal public release	4th QTR 22			
1.7 Document provenance				
ACTRIS: first test version	4th QTR 22			
ACTRIS: final version	4th QTR 22			
Task where implementation plan is needed				
2.1 Domain vocabulary / ontology	3rd QTR 22			
2.2 Documentation of provenance	1st QTR 21			
2.3 Recommendations for licenses	3rd QTR 22			
2.4 Semantic search				

Table 3: Summary of implementation of FAIRness within ACTRIS -In-Situ

Task and Milestones under implementation	Due month Implementation plan	Status June 2020	Status November 2022	Status February 2023
1.1 Use of PIDs throughout workflow				
ACTRIS: determine PID solution	3rd QTR 20	●	●	●
ACTRIS: implement primary DOIs	4th QTR 20	●	●	●
ACTRIS: PIDs pre-products implemented	2nd QTR 21	●	●	●
ACTRIS: ORCID and org. PIDs implemented	4th QTR 21	●	●	●
1.2 Standard interfaces for (meta)data access				
ACTRIS: metadata repository, 1st version	4th QTR 20	●	●	●
ACTRIS: metadata M2M interface available	1st QTR 21	●	●	●
1.3 Data indexing in WIS and GEOSS				
ACTRIS: link to GISC in WIS implemented	3rd QTR 21	●	●	●
1.4 Common authentication schemes				
ACTRIS: ORCID authentication implemented	4th QTR 21	●	●	●
Task where implementation plan is needed				
2.1 Domain vocabulary / ontology	1st QTR 21	●	●	●
2.2 Documentation of provenance	1st QTR 21	●	●	●
2.3 Recommendations for licenses	1st QTR 21	●	●	●
2.4 Semantic search	1st QTR 21	●	●	●
2.5 Graphical user interfaces	1st QTR 21	●	●	●

Table 4: Summary of implementation of FAIRness within ACTRIS -ARES

Task and Milestones under implementation	Due month Implementati on plan	Status June 2020	Status November 2022	Status February 2023
1.1 Use of PIDs throughout workflow				
ACTRIS: determine PID solution	3rd QTR 20	●	●	●
ACTRIS: implement primary DOIs	4th QTR 20	●	●	●
ACTRIS: PIDs pre-products implemented	2nd QTR 21	●	●	●
ACTRIS: ORCID and org. PIDs implemented	4th QTR 21	●	●	●
1.2 Standard interfaces for (meta)data access				
ACTRIS: metadata repository, 1st version	4th QTR 20	●	●	●
ACTRIS: metadata M2M interface available	1st QTR 21	●	●	●
1.3 Data indexing in WIS and GEOSS				
ACTRIS: link to GISC in WIS implemented	3rd QTR 21	●	●	●
1.4 Common authentication schemes				
ACTRIS: ORCID authentication implemented	4th QTR 21	●	●	●
Task where implementation plan is needed				
2.1 Domain vocabulary / ontology	1st QTR 21	●	●	●
2.2 Documentation of provenance	1st QTR 21	●	●	●
2.3 Recommendations for licenses	1st QTR 21	●	●	●
2.4 Semantic search	1st QTR 21	●	●	●
2.5 Graphical user interfaces	1st QTR 21	●	●	●

Table 5: Summary of implementation of FAIRness within ACTRIS -CLU

Task and Milestones under implementation	Due month Implementati on plan	Status June 2020	Status November 2022	Status February 2023
1.1 Use of PIDs throughout workflow				
ACTRIS: determine PID solution	3rd QTR 20	●	●	●
ACTRIS: implement primary DOIs	4th QTR 20	●	●	●
ACTRIS: PIDs pre-products implemented	2nd QTR 21	●	●	●
ACTRIS: ORCID and org. PIDs implemented	4th QTR 21	●	●	●
1.2 Standard interfaces for (meta)data access				
ACTRIS: metadata repository, 1st version	4th QTR 20	●	●	●
ACTRIS: metadata M2M interface available	1st QTR 21	●	●	●
1.3 Data indexing in WIS and GEOSS				
ACTRIS: link to GISC in WIS implemented	3rd QTR 21	●	●	●
1.4 Common authentication schemes				
ACTRIS: ORCID authentication implemented	4th QTR 21	●	●	●
Task where implementation plan is needed				
2.1 Domain vocabulary / ontology	1st QTR 21	●	●	●
2.2 Documentation of provenance	1st QTR 21	●	●	●
2.3 Recommendations for licenses	1st QTR 21	●	●	●
2.4 Semantic search	1st QTR 21	●	●	●
2.5 Graphical user interfaces	1st QTR 21	●	●	●

Table 6: Summary of implementation of FAIRness within ACTRIS -GRES

Task and Milestones under implementation	Due month Implementati on plan	Status June 2020	Status November 2022	Status February 2023
1.1 Use of PIDs throughout workflow				
ACTRIS: determine PID solution	3rd QTR 20			
ACTRIS: implement primary DOIs	4th QTR 20			
ACTRIS: PIDs pre-products implemented	2nd QTR 21			
ACTRIS: ORCID and org. PIDs implemented	4th QTR 21			
1.2 Standard interfaces for (meta)data access				
ACTRIS: metadata repository, 1st version	4th QTR 20			
ACTRIS: metadata M2M interface available	1st QTR 21			
1.3 Data indexing in WIS and GEOSS				
ACTRIS: link to GISC in WIS implemented	3rd QTR 21			
1.4 Common authentication schemes				
ACTRIS: ORCID authentication implemented	4th QTR 21			
Task where implementation plan is needed				
2.1 Domain vocabulary / ontology	1st QTR 21			
2.2 Documentation of provenance	1st QTR 21			
2.3 Recommendations for licenses	1st QTR 21			
2.4 Semantic search	1st QTR 21			
2.5 Graphical user interfaces	1st QTR 21			

Table 7: Summary of implementation of FAIRness within ACTRIS -ASC

Task and Milestones under implementation	Due month Implementation plan	Status June 2020	Status November 2022	Status February 2023
1.1 Use of PIDs throughout workflow				
ACTRIS: determine PID solution	3rd QTR 20			
ACTRIS: implement primary DOIs	4th QTR 20			
ACTRIS: PIDs pre-products implemented	2nd QTR 21			
ACTRIS: ORCID and org. PIDs implemented	4th QTR 21			
1.2 Standard interfaces for (meta)data access				
ACTRIS: metadata repository, 1st version	4th QTR 20			
ACTRIS: metadata M2M interface available	1st QTR 21			
1.3 Data indexing in WIS and GEOSS				
ACTRIS: link to GISC in WIS implemented	*			
1.4 Common authentication schemes				
ACTRIS: ORCID authentication implemented	4th QTR 21			
Task where implementation plan is needed				
2.1 Domain vocabulary / ontology	1st QTR 21			
2.2 Documentation of provenance	1st QTR 21			
2.3 Recommendations for licenses	1st QTR 21			
2.4 Semantic search	1st QTR 21			
2.5 Graphical user interfaces	1st QTR 21			

*Note – topic 1.3 it not relevant for the ASC data centre units.

2.1.2 EISCAT-3D and the progress of FAIRness over the period 2019 – 2022

The EISCAT_3D radar system is a major upgrade of the capabilities of EISCAT Scientific Association. At the time when the ENVRI-FAIR project was conceived, the first EISCAT_3D data were expected to be available to the user community towards the end of 2021. However, significant delays in the construction of the EISCAT_3D system due to factors such as the CoViD-19 pandemic and the global shortage of semi-conductor components has had the effect that the EISCAT_3D system is still under construction. Hence, there have been no EISCAT_3D data available at any point during the ENVRI-FAIR project. For that reason, a significant part of the work in the ENVRI-FAIR project has been focused on the status of the data from the present EISCAT systems.

Table 8: Summary of implementation of FAIRness for EISCAT_3D

Task and Milestones under implementation	Due month	Progress		
		MS40	MS42	MS44
1.1 Use of PIDs throughout workflow				
EISCAT: determine DOI granularity	4th QTR 21			
EISCAT: product DOIs implemented	1st QTR 22			
EISCAT: PID publication	2nd QTR 22			
1.2 Standard interfaces for (meta)data access				
EISCAT: DataCite metadata defined (Level 3)	2nd QTR 20			
EISCAT: DataCite metadata defined (Level 1&2)	4th QTR 21			
EISCAT: metadata ingested in B2FIND	1st QTR 22			
EISCAT: OAI-PMH interface available	1st QTR 22			
1.3 Data indexing in WIS and GEOSS				
EISCAT: ontology updated	4th QTR 21			
EISCAT: set up WIS compatible metadata	4th QTR 21			
EISCAT: link to WIS established	4th QTR 21			
1.4 Common authentication schemes				
EISCAT: authentication for operations	2nd QTR 21			
EISCAT: authentication for data	4th QTR 21			
EISCAT: authentication for processing	4th QTR 21			
1.5 Service endpoint to ENVRI-hub				
EISCAT: Update to Madrigal 3	1st QTR 21			
EISCAT: Harmonise Madrigal APIs with ENVRI	2nd QTR 22			
EISCAT: Implement APIs for all data levels	4th QTR 22			
1.6 GUI recommendations				
EISCAT: database upgrade	2nd QTR 21			
EISCAT: new data format	3rd QTR 21			
EISCAT: AAI implemented	4th QTR 21			
EISCAT: new portal implemented	3rd QTR 22			
1.7 Document provenance				
EISCAT: new data format, more provenance	4th QTR 21			
EISCAT: use PIDs	1st QTR 22			
Task where implementation plan is needed				
2.1 Domain vocabulary / ontology	3rd QTR 22			
2.2 Documentation of provenance	1st QTR 21			
2.3 Recommendations for licenses	1st QTR 21			
2.4 Semantic search	1st QTR 21			
2.5 Graphical user interfaces	3rd QTR 22			

2.1.3 IAGOS Data Centre and the progress of FAIRness over the period 2019 – 2022

Since the beginning of ENVRI-FAIR, IAGOS conducted four FAIRness assessments using the FIPs in 2019, 2020 and 2021 and the last finished April 2023. Based on the gap analysis and the first FIP, a detailed implementation plan was developed for IAGOS. The main gaps that have been identified for IAGOS were:

- No use of PIDs in the IAGOS data processing workflow
- No implementation of standard interfaces for metadata and data access
- No common authentication scheme with the other RIs implemented
- No documentation of the provenance

A new version of the IAGOS data portal was already planned at the beginning of ENVRI-FAIR. All the developments were aligned with the implementation plan. The regular assessments allowed to monitor the progress of IAGOS FAIRness during the project and check the consistency with the implementation plan.

Table 9: Summary of implementation of FAIRness for IAGOS

IAGOS				
Progress on implementation of FAIRness	March 2023			
Completed				
In progress				
Not started, according to plan				
New task, not in the implementation plan				
Task and Milestones under implementation	Due month	2020	2021	2022
Implementation plan				
1.1 Use of PIDs throughout workflow				
IAGOS: ePIC registration, internal ORCID PIDs	2nd QTR 21			
IAGOS: definition of workflow, incl. PID	3rd QTR 20			
IAGOS: workflow with PIDs, implemented	4th QTR 21			
IAGOS: implement ORCID and ROR	4th QTR 21			
IAGOS: management of DOI fragments	4th QTR 21			
1.2 Standard interfaces for (meta)data access				
IAGOS: REST API for metadata access implemented.	4th QTR 21			
IAGOS: THREDDS server for data access implemented.	2nd QTR 23			
IAGOS: REST API for data access implemented	4th QTR 21			
1.3 Data indexing in WIS and GEOSS				
IAGOS: WIGOS metadata implemented	2nd QTR 23			
IAGOS: link to WIS established	4th QTR 22			
1.4 Common authentication schemes				
IAGOS: ORCID / eduGAIN authentication avail.	1st QTR 22			
1.5 Service endpoint to ENVRI-hub				
IAGOS: set up PythonAPI endpoint	4th QTR 21			
IAGOS: provide service record	1st QTR 23			
1.6 GUI recommendations				
IAGOS: release of new portal	1st QTR 22			
1.7 Document provenance				
IAGOS: management of DOI fragments	4th QTR 21			
IAGOS: consistent use of PIDs	4th QTR 21			
IAGOS: new IAGOS Data Portal	1st QTR 22			
Task where implementation plan is needed				
2.1 Domain vocabulary / ontology	3rd QTR 22			
2.2 Documentation of provenance	1st QTR 22			
2.3 Recommendations for licenses	1st QTR 22			
2.4 Semantic search	1st QTR 21			
2.5 Graphical user interfaces	1st QTR 22			

2.1.4 ICOS Carbon Portal and the progress of FAIRness over the period 2019 – 2022

The gaps identified for improvement of the fairness of the ICOS data repository concern mainly relatively small details and refinements that nevertheless are important for implementing future machine to machine interoperability. Until now the main emphasis in the development had been on pure functionality through a robust, flexible and modern core (back-end), and achieving a high scalability and performance of the system. Next steps are on core functionalities for the users, for access, preview and attribution of the data providers.

Table 10: Summary of implementation of FAIRness for ICOS

ICOS				
Progress on implementaion of FAIRness		April 2023		
Completed				
In progress				
Not started, according to plan				
Delay				
		Due month		
Task and Milestones under implementation	Implementation	2020	2021	2022
1.1 Use of PIDs throughout workflow				
ORCID & ROR, integration DOI and Handle PID				
1.2 Standard interfaces for (meta)data access				
ICOS: metadata for Google search published	3rd QTR 20			
ICOS: OAI-PMH metadata server implemented	4th QTR 20			
ICOS: publish ICOS controlled vocabulary	4th QTR 20			
ICOS: implement WIS metadata provision	4th QTR 20			
ICOS: implement link to external documents	2nd QTR 21			
ICOS: implement license as resolvable URL	4th QTR 21			
ICOS: full provenance metadata implemented	1st QTR 22			
ICOS: REST API for data subsetting implemented	4th QTR 21			
ICOS: NetCDF-CF data export implemented	4th QTR 20			
ICOS: THREDDS server updated	1st QTR 22			
ICOS: increased search capabilities in interface	3rd QTR 20			
1.3 Data indexing in WIS and GEOSS				
ICOS: link to GEOSS established	n.a.			
1.4 Common authentication schemes				
ICOS: common authentication implemented	4th QTR 21			
Task where implementation plan is needed				
2.1 Domain vocabulary / ontology	3rd QTR 22			
2.2 Documentation of provenance	1st QTR 21			
2.3 Recommendations for licenses	1st QTR 21			
2.4 Semantic search	1st QTR 21			
2.5 Graphical user interfaces	3rd QTR 22			

2.1.5 SIOS and the progress of FAIRness over the period 2019 – 2022

SIOS is a regional observing system for long-term measurements in and around Svalbard, with the scope of integrating existing data centres through a distributed data management system (SDMS) which harvests, indexes and makes available data from different contributing centers. Each data centre has its own procedures and technical solutions tailored to the needs and the use of that data centre. Although SIOS does not own data, it serves as a central node where metadata records are harvested and exposed to the community. SIOS also is responsible for promoting FAIRness within the data centres, as well as for providing added value services through human and machine interfaces. An initial assessment of the FAIRness status within SIOS has highlighted some strengths, but also some weaknesses that could be improved through the ENVRI-FAIR project and served as basis for the implementation plan within WP8.

Table 11: Summary of implementation of FAIRness for SIOS

Task and Milestones under implementation	Due month			
	Implementation plan	2020	2022	Final
1.1 Use of PIDs throughout workflow				
SIOS: METNO supports DOI minting	1st QTR 20	●	●	●
1.2 Standard interfaces for (meta)data access				
SIOS: deploy pyCSW software	3rd QTR 20	●	●	●
SIOS: indexing of METNO data in pycsw	4th QTR 20	●	●	●
SIOS: impl. OAI-PMH at NILU and CNR	2nd QTR 22	●	●	●
SIOS: partner data in central pycsw	4th QTR 21	●	●	●
SIOS: translation to INSPIRE	1st QTR 22	●	●	●
SIOS: translation to WMO Core	2nd QTR 22	●	●	●
SIOS: NILU OPeNDAP implementation	4th QTR 20	●	●	●
SIOS: CNR OPeNDAP implementation	2nd QTR 22	●	●	●
SIOS: support link to WIGOS	2nd QTR 20	●	●	●
SIOS: update indexing engine	4th QTR 21	●	●	●
1.3 Data indexing in WIS and GEOSS				
SIOS: indexing in WIS and GEOSS	4th QTR 22	●	●	●
1.4 Common authentication schemes				
SIOS: implementation of SSO (orcid)	4th QTR 22	●	●	●
1.5 Service endpoint to ENVRI-hub				
SIOS: set up PythonAPI endpoint	3rd QTR 21	●	●	●
SIOS: provide service records	4th QTR 22	●	●	●
1.6 GUI recommendations				
SIOS: release of new data portal	3rd QTR 21	●	●	●
SIOS: link data portal to vocabulary server	2nd QTR 22	●	●	●
1.7 Document provenance				
SIOS: Expose provenance information	4th QTR 22	●	●	●
1.8 Domain vocabulary / ontology				
SIOS: Domain vocabulary / ontology	3rd QTR 22	●	●	●
1.9 Recommendation for licenses				
SIOS: licenses	1st QTR 21	●	●	●

2.2 The atmospheric FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) and convergence across the subdomain

In addition to the RI specific implementation of FAIRness, progress of convergence across the subdomain by implementation of common solutions has been an important goal. Harmonization across the RIs is an important principle to serve broad type of use and users, and we work to improve access for more easily combination of data, information and facilitate interdisciplinary science. Harmonized solutions across the subdomain facilitate the development of joint products and services utilizing data and data products from each RI. Furthermore, common solutions will also benefit the users greatly lowering the threshold for accessing data products and facilitates the link of services and data products to EOSC, and other European and global initiatives.

A commonly used measure of FAIRness and FAIRness convergence is the FAIR convergence matrix. The FAIR Convergence Matrix is a platform that systematically guides any self-identified community (in this case the ENVRI community) in the decision process leading to optimal FAIR implementations and practices. The resulting collection of FAIR implementation choices composes the FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP) for that community. One important concept for this assessment is the “the single FER (fair enabling resources) of a given subprinciple”. Accordingly, for each of the principles **F**indable – **A**ssessable – **I**nteroperable **R**eusable, there is defined a list of predefined FERs across the project.

Convergence across the atmospheric subdomain and implementation of commons solutions are monitored and assessed using FIPs. Within the ENVRI community these profiles are represented by 21 questions asked to the data steward of a community to assess the FAIRness of resources. see Table 1. When a question is answered with an existing resource, or a resource that is in development, it is then considered as a FAIR-enabling resource (FER) which determines if a FAIR principle is met or not. Several FERs can meet the same FAIR principle. All FERs are associated to a status at the RI levels, the shared FER status with the status values:

- 0 - Resource not declared by community
- 1 - Resource in development, future use
- 2 - existing Resource, future use
- 3 - existing Resource, current use

Over the period 2019- 2023 there were 4 FAIR assessments documenting the progress of convergence.

Table 12: Questionnaire used to define the FIP within ENVRI-FAIR. *MD = meta data, D = Data*

FAIR principle*	Question	FAIR enabling resource types
F1-MD	What globally unique, persistent, resolvable identifiers do you use for metadata records?	Identifier type
F1-D	What globally unique, persistent, resolvable identifiers do you use for datasets?	Identifier type
F2	Which metadata schemes do you use for findability?	Metadata scheme
F3	What is the technology that links the persistent identifiers of your data to the metadata description?	Metadata-Data linking mechanism
F4-MD	In which search engines are your metadata records indexed?	Search engines
F4-D	In which search engines are your datasets indexed?	Search engines
A1.1-MD	Which standardized communication protocol do you use for metadata records?	Communication protocol
A1.1-D	Which standardized communication protocol do you use for datasets?	Communication protocol
A1.2-MD	Which authentication & authorisation technique do you use for metadata records?	Authentication & authorisation technique
A1.2-D	Which authentication & authorisation technique do you use for datasets?	Authentication & authorisation technique
A2	Which metadata longevity plan do you use?	Metadata longevity plan
I1-MD	Which knowledge representation languages (allowing machine interoperation) do you use for metadata records?	Knowledge representation language
I1-D	Which knowledge representation languages (allowing machine interoperation) do you use for datasets?	Knowledge representation language
I2-MD	Which structured vocabularies do you use to annotate your metadata records?	Structured vocabularies
I2-D	Which structured vocabularies do you use to encode your datasets?	Structured vocabularies
I3-MD	Which models, schema(s) do you use for metadata records?	Metadata schema
I3-D	Which models, schema(s) do you use for datasets?	Data schema
R1.1-MD	Which usage license do you use for metadata records?	Data usage license
R1.1-D	Which usage license do you use for datasets?	Data usage license
R1.2-MD	Which metadata schemas do you use for describing the provenance of your metadata records?	Provenance model
R1.2-D	Which metadata schemas do you use for describing the provenance of your datasets?	Provenance model

* see section 1.1 for description of subprinciples

In order to provide a most complete overview of the FAIRness level, different metrics were used:

- **convergence matrix** on common technologies used in FERs among the different RIs, their state of development (0-3 as defined above)
- **FIP per RI and the total number of FERs completed each year** by each RI documents the progress (section 2"X)

These is assessment using FIPs were performed 4 times over the period 2019 – 2023.

2.2.1 The implemented FAIR-enabling resources (FERs)

This section documents the most used FAIR Enabling Resources (FERs) in the atmospheric sub-domain, and the status of the implementation. Table 13 shows the implementation profile per repository at start, and towards end of the project (April 2023). Values are the average implementation status of the single FER of a given subprinciple.

Table 13: Implementation profile per repository at start in 2019, and status April 2023. Values are the average implementation status of the single FER (fair enabling resources) of a given subprinciple (see 1.1 for definitions).

2019												
mean status												
		ACTRIS_CU	ACTRIS_DVAS	ACTRIS_GRES	ACTRIS_InSitu	ACTRIS-ARES	ACTRIS-ASC	EISCAT	iaigos	ICDS	sigs	
F	F1	F1-D			2,0			3,0	2,0	3,0	3,0	3,0
		F1-MD			2,2			3,0		2,0	3,0	3,0
	F2	F2	3,0	2,0	2,6	3,0	3,0	2,6	2,0	2,7	3,0	2,0
	F3	F3			2,0			2,0		2,0		
	F4	F4-D			2,0			2,0		3,0		
		F4-MD			2,0			2,0	2,0	2,7	3,0	
A	A1	A1.1-D		3,0	2,7	3,0	3,0	2,8	3,0	2,1	3,0	3,0
		A1.1-MD	2,0	3,0	2,8	3,0	3,0	3,0		2,5	2,8	2,0
	A1.2-D	3,0		3,0	3,0		3,0		2,0	3,0	3,0	
	A1.2-MD	3,0		3,0	3,0		3,0		2,0	3,0	3,0	
I	I1	I1-D	3,0		2,0		3,0	2,0		3,0	3,0	3,0
		I1-MD	3,0		3,0	3,0	3,0	3,0		2,6	3,0	3,0
	I2	I2-D					3,0			3,0	3,0	
		I2-MD	3,0		3,0	2,0		3,0		3,0		3,0
	I3	I3-D	3,0		2,0		3,0	2,0		3,0	3,0	3,0
		I3-MD			3,0	3,0		3,0		2,8		3,0
R	R1	R1.1-D	3,0							2,0	3,0	3,0
		R1.1-MD									3,0	
	R1.2	R1.2-D					3,0		2,0	2,0	2,0	
		R1.2-MD					3,0			2,0	2,0	

2022												
mean status												
		ACTRIS_CU	ACTRIS_DVAS	ACTRIS_GRES	ACTRIS_InSitu	ACTRIS-ARES	ACTRIS-ASC	EISCAT	iaigos	ICDS	sigs	
F	F1	F1-D	2,3	3,0	2,9	3,0	3,0	3,0	3,0	3,0	3,0	3,0
		F1-MD	3,0	3,0	3,0	3,0	2,9	3,0		3,0	3,0	3,0
	F2	F2	3,0	3,0	3,0	3,0	2,7	3,0		2,8	3,0	3,0
	F3	F3	3,0	3,0	3,0	3,0	3,0	3,0		3,0		
	F4	F4-D		3,0	3,0	3,0	2,6	3,0		2,5	3,0	2,1
		F4-MD		3,0	3,0	3,0	2,7	3,0	2,0	2,6	3,0	2,1
A	A1	A1.1-D	3,0	3,0	2,9	3,0	3,0	2,7	2,1	2,7	3,0	3,0
		A1.1-MD	3,0	3,0	2,8	3,0	3,0	3,0	3,0	3,0	2,8	3,0
	A1.2-D	3,0		3,0	3,0	2,0	3,0	3,0	3,0	3,0	3,0	
	A1.2-MD	3,0		3,0	3,0	2,0	3,0		3,0	3,0	3,0	
A2	A2	3,0	3,0	3,0	3,0	3,0	3,0					
I	I1	I1-D	3,0	3,0	3,0	3,0	3,0	2,0		3,0	3,0	3,0
		I1-MD	3,0	3,0	3,0	3,0	3,0	3,0		3,0	3,0	3,0
	I2	I2-D	2,0		3,0	2,7	2,0	2,0		3,0		3,0
		I2-MD	2,3	1,	2,4	2,3	2,0	2,4		3,0		3,0
	I3	I3-D	3,0		3,0	3,0	3,0	2,0		3,0	3,0	3,0
		I3-MD			3,0	3,0	2,3	3,0	2,5	2,8		3,0
R	R1	R1.1-D	3,0	3,0	3,0	3,0	3,0	3,0		3,0	3,0	3,0
		R1.1-MD	3,0	3,0	3,0		3,0	3,0		3,0	3,0	
	R1.2	R1.2-D		2,0	2,0	2,0	3,0	2,0	2,1	2,0	3,0	
		R1.2-MD	2,0	2,0	3,0	2,0	3,0	2,0	2,5	2,0	3,0	

Figure 2a: The count of FERs any pair of RIs has in common for Findable – upper panel, Accessible in lower panel.

Figure 2b: The count of FERs any pair of RIs has in common for **I**nteroperable in upper panel and **R**e-usable in the lower panel.

Figure 3 shows the number of FERs any pair of RI data centre has in common. E.g, one vocabulary and one particular CC-license would sum up to a shared FER count = 2. Values are aggregated per principle, year etc. by totalling the number of shared FERs, not taking into account the implementation status. Plots for all years and all FERs are shown.

The strong progress in FAIRness across the sub-domain is evident, in particular for the categories “Findable” and Re-usable”. For these principles the RIs was more or less starting from scratch with respect to the FERs defined for the full environmental domain (section 1.2).

Analysing these plots in relation to the tables in section 2.1, it is possible to check each RI’s implementation tasks over the period, and the largest development, and which implementation steps that has been implemented on the repository level to improve the atmospheric FAIRness and convergence with the other RIs.

2.2.2 Convergence of FAIRness within the atmospheric subdomain

The documentation of the improved convergence across the atmospheric subdomain is included in Figure 4. The values given are average implementation status of the list of predefined FERs used to monitor the implementation of FAIRness. The plots are also called “heat maps”.

The shared FER status with the status values 0 – 3 (0=Resource not declared by community. 1 = Resource in development, future use, 2 = existing Resource, future use. 3 - existing Resource, current use). Figure 4 shows the FAIR convergence from 2019 – 2022.

Figure 4a: The convergence matrix for the atmospheric subdomain showing the development of joint solutions divided in “Findable – upper panel, Accessible in lower panel.

Figure 4b: The convergence matrix for the atmospheric subdomain showing the development of joint solutions dividen in Interoperable in panel 1 and Re-usable in the lower panel.

Figure 5 The convergence matrix for the atmospheric subdomain showing the accumulated status for all FAIR sub-principles.

Figure 4 and 5 documents the evolution and the strong progress of convergence within the atmospheric sub-domain over the period. The sub-domain has successfully implemented many harmonised solutions, and as seen in Table 12 most are also finally implemented (also seen in the heat maps).

Figure 5 showing the convergence matrix for the atmospheric subdomain based on averaging numbers and the accumulated status for all FAIR sub-principles, is not very illustrative, as the atmospheric subdomain was mature in some aspects and principles from the start and many RIs had worked on implementation of FAIR tasks before the first FER assessments. Accordingly, the pattern was hidden behind the solutions ready from early of the project. However, looking at Figure 2 and Figure 4, the strong evolution and progress of FAIRness are evident and well documented over all years, and all sub-principles.

Describing this in more detail, from the matrix, with the “Accessible” panel 2 in Figure 4 it is evident that all the involved data centres offered relatively good and proper access to data from the start of ENVIR-FAIR in 2019, and that this has been a priority for the RIs at an early stage and the RIs was relatively mature with respect to this. However, looking at panel 1 in Figure 2 showing the development of the FERs for “Findable data” there has been a strong development in all RIs, and also Figure 4 panel 1 documents the high convergence across the RI for this principle. This is a very important objective and achievement for the subdomain as for the users commons solutions in the way of identifying and finding the data is important.

For “Re-Useable” FERs the development and achievements over the period 2019-2022 has been extremely strong. One example of important achievements is the establishment of a community standard for the use of licence on data; in practical terms all are using CCBY 4. This is an important joint solution, facilitating the possibility of developing new products and services across the subdomain.

2.3 The atmospheric subdomain compared to the other environmental domains.

It is interesting also to compare the work and evolution within the atmospheric subdomain with the progress and convergence with the RIs in the other environmental domains.

The figure below shows the environmental RIs, and some are multi-domain like ICOS and SIOS, so the RIs are not associated to specific compartments. A description of the RIs can be found here: [Research Infrastructures – ENVRI Community](#)

Figure 6: Overview of all the RIs participating in ENVIR-FAIR and the cross-RI FARIness assessments.

Figure 7 Implementation and convergence for the atmospheric subdomain compared to the other environmental domains. The numbers are the number of FERs any pair of RI data centre has in common. E.g, one vocabulary and one particular CC-license would sum up to a shared FER count = 2. Only the accumulated values for all FAIR principles are shown. The atmospheric RIs and the multicomponent RIs with atmospheric component are shown in light blue.

Figure 7 shows the evolution of convergence for the atmospheric subdomain compared to the other environmental domains. The atmospheric RIs and the multicomponent RIs with atmospheric component are shown with light blue background. This figure documents that the atmospheric subdomain has made great achievements with many common solutions also with other subdomains. Additionally, the plots shows that atmospheric subdomain has made strong progress also compared to the evolution of the other sub-domains within the environmental community.

With exception of ICOS, for the atmospheric subdomain, the categories “Findable” and Re-usable” was pre-mature at the start of the project (see Figure 2 at page 23Figure 4). For these principles the RIs was more or less starting on scratch with the respect to the FERs defined, and the progress is very high.

The ENVRI community has been of invaluable important for the development and shared solutions truly accelerating the development and implementation of common, harmonised solutions and concepts, to the benefit of all users and facilitates a more well-organised and efficient link to EOSC and others.

3 Main achievements for the atmospheric subdomain

Section 2 documents the strong progress and evolution of FAIRness within the atmospheric sub-domain, and convergence to common solutions.

This section highlights the *joint* achievements across the sub-domain opening new opportunities and synergies. The convergence in many FAIR aspects has led to improved development of cross RI/subdomain products:

- Seamless integration across the atmospheric sub-domain for our users on many aspects
- Possible to implement cross RI services thanks to **the convergence between RIs** on important topics such as vocabularies, identifiers or licences.
- Controlled vocabulary extending beyond our RI that has enabled better integration with other RIs and subdomains. This has also helped/forced us to be more precise in defining the terms we use.
- Common concept for use of PIDs, not only for data products, but also other entities involved in data production.

Figure 8: Joint achievements across the atmospheric subdomain

The next illustration highlights the atmospheric subdomain achievements towards the ENVRI-FAIR goals.

Figure 9: Atmospheric subdomain achievements towards the ENVRI-FAIR goals

To be noted that major services developed by the Research Infrastructures (RIs), including cross-RI services, have been described in the ENVRI Catalogue of services, as well as in the EOSC Marketplace. The current status of the cataloguing is detailed in “Milestone MS51 - Atmospheric subdomain services in service catalogue for exposure to EOSC”.

3.1 What can we do now which we could not do before advancing of the FAIRness?

This section includes references to a few examples on what we can do now, with services that have been implemented or improved utilising the development documents in section 2. The main driver for this work was to develop a FAIR ENVRI atmospheric data demonstrator to support the needs for data from all involved RIs during extreme events. The aim of the FAIR ENVRI atmospheric data demonstrator is to shorten time response in providing scientific analysis of an extreme event and harmonised dataset and tools. Figure 10 shows examples of 2 events where a combination of data and data products across the atmospheric subdomain is highly valuable to detect and assess the risks for human and society.

Figure 10: Atmospheric hazards like Saharan dust intrusion (upper panel) and fires (lower panel) is guiding the development of the demonstrator for improved FAIRness (satellite pictures from ESA)

The FAIR ENVRI Atmospheric Data Demonstrator has been developed to showcase data interoperability within the Atmosphere subdomain. This demonstrator has been developed in the frame of the Task 8.5: "Demonstrate Atmospheric subdomain FAIRness." The successful implementation of FAIR principles by all participating RIs, as previously presented, enabled the development of this service.

For example, all participating RIs (ACTRIS, IAGOS, ICOS, and SIOS) have implemented a shared library for metadata and data access. This ensures a consistent and unified approach to accessing metadata and data across the RIs. Additionally, the establishment of a common data license among the RIs and the mapping of variables to the Essential Climate Variables (ECV) were crucial for the implementation process.

For more detailed information about the demonstrator, please refer to the deliverable "D8.9 - Demonstrator of implemented service".

Figure 11: Screenshot of the FAIR demonstrator - e.g., ICOS and IAGOS data comparison over Paris

With the significant FAIRness achievements within the subdomain also improved links to satellite community is possible, and a very valuable use case. Many applications need to match ground-based observations with collocated satellite observations:

- Dealing with the complexity of satellite orbits, viewing geometry, data format, etc. is very challenging for most users
- Need for a collocation service capable of identifying satellite observations that match ground-based measurements, given a list of stations and user-specified collocation criteria

To interpret atmospheric concentration at a station one needs to know the spatial region/source area that influences the air mass that is being measured at the station. Hence, with the convergence within the subdomain we can now improve satellite data extraction and collocation through machine-to-machine interoperable services in a more harmonised way, combining ground based and satellite data more easily. A collocation service has been implemented in the frame of the Task 8.5. A short description is available in Deliverable “D8.11 - Portfolio of subdomain web-processing services”.

Accordingly, with the convergence within the subdomain we can now improve satellite data extraction and collocation through machine to machine interoperable services in a more harmonised way, combining ground based and satellite data more easily.